

ISic0034

I.Sicily inscription 0034

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

sarcophagus

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Panhormus

Place of origin (modern)

Palermo

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 3534

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [D(is)] M(anibus)
2. [---]f(iliae) · Festivae
3. [---][e]t · uxori · rariss(imae) [---]
4. [---] Mercur[ui]s

Apparatus

Text of

Mommsen read the first letter of line 2 as 'e', and restores the text as .

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491811

EDR 137868

EDCS 22100014

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. *Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum.* Berlin. At 10.7311 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650793>)

Bivona, L. 1970. *Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. Sikelia.* Palermo. At 34

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0034. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4333847>